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Review Article

Ashwagandha (*Withania somnifera*), Taxonomy, Pharmacological Properties and Its Role in COVID-19 and Extraction Process: A Comprehensive Expansion

Yash Srivastav*, Samsheer Bahadur Bind, Aditya Srivastav

Azad Institute of Pharmacy & Research, Lucknow, U.P., India

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ABSTRACT

Ayurvedic medicine frequently uses ashwagandha, usually referred to as Indian ginseng or *Withania somnifera*. It has long been used to enhance memory and cognitive function, lessen stress and anxiety, and boost stamina and endurance. Numerous investigations into the possible advantages of ashwagandha have been carried out. For instance, the ashwagandha administration significantly reduced stress and anxiety symptoms in individuals with a history of chronic stress, according to a 2016 study published in the *Journal of Dietary Supplements*. It is crucial to remember that even if ashwagandha might have certain advantages, further study is required to completely comprehend its effects and the ideal dosage. Before beginning to utilize any supplement, it's crucial to consult a healthcare provider.

INTRODUCTION

Ashwagandha, also known as "Indian ginseng," is an herb commonly used in Ayurvedic medicine. It is believed to have a variety of health benefits, including reducing stress and anxiety, improving brain function, and increasing endurance and strength. The roots and berries of the ashwagandha plant are used in traditional medicine. It is also available in supplement form and is often used to support overall well-being. Ashwagandha is considered generally safe for most people when

used in the short term, but more research is needed to determine its long-term safety and effectiveness (1)

***Corresponding Author:** Yash Srivastav

Address: 13Azad Institute of Pharmacy & Research, Lucknow, U.P., India.

Email ✉: neelashsrv76@gmail.com

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Fig. 1: Ashwagandha (*Withania somnifera*) plant

Ashwagandha, also known as *Withania somnifera* or Indian ginseng, is a popular herb in Ayurvedic medicine that has been used for centuries to promote overall health and well-being. The roots and berries of the ashwagandha plant are used in traditional medicine to help reduce stress and anxiety, improve brain function, and increase endurance and strength. It is also believed to have anti-inflammatory and antioxidant properties. Ashwagandha is available in supplement form, including capsules, tablets, and powder. It is considered generally safe for most people when used in the short-term (2).

History of Ashwagandha

Ashwagandha, also known as *Withania somnifera*, has a long history of use in Ayurvedic medicine, a traditional system of medicine that originated in India over 3,000 years ago. The herb is mentioned in ancient Indian texts such as the Charaka Samhita and the Sushruta Samhita, where it is described as a "rasayana," a group of herbs believed to promote overall health and longevity. The name "ashwagandha" comes from the Sanskrit words "ashva," meaning horse, and "gandha," meaning smell, referring to the herb's distinct smell and the belief that it can give the strength and vitality of a horse. Ashwagandha has been traditionally used to treat a wide range of health conditions, including stress and anxiety, insomnia, and fatigue. It is also believed to have anti-inflammatory and antioxidant properties and to improve brain function, memory, and overall well-being. In recent years, ashwagandha has gained

popularity as a dietary supplement and has been the subject of numerous scientific studies. These studies have found that ashwagandha may have potential health benefits, including reducing stress and anxiety, improving cognitive function, increasing muscle mass and strength, and reducing inflammation. However, more research is needed to confirm these findings and to determine the long-term safety and effectiveness of ashwagandha (3).

Taxonomical Classification of Ashwagandha

Ashwagandha, also known as *Withania somnifera*, belongs to the plant family Solanaceae. It is a perennial shrub that grows to a height of about 1-1.5 meters. It has green or gray-green leaves and small, greenish-yellow flowers that grow in clusters. The plant produces red or orange-red berries that are used for medicinal purposes.

Taxonomically, it is classified as:

Kingdom: Plantae Order: Solanales Family: Solanaceae Genus: *Withania* Species: *W. somnifera*.

Growing Areas in the Country

Ashwagandha, also known as *Withania somnifera*, is native to the dry regions of India, North Africa, and the Middle East. It is typically grown in arid and semi-arid regions, and can tolerate poor soil conditions and drought. In India, Ashwagandha is mainly grown in the states of Rajasthan, Gujarat, and Madhya Pradesh. Some of the other states where it is grown are Maharashtra, Uttar Pradesh, and Haryana. It is also cultivated in many other countries like Nepal, China, and Yemen (4).

Origin, Geographical Distribution

Ashwagandha, also known as *Withania somnifera*, is a perennial shrub that is native to the dry regions of India, North Africa, and the Middle East. It is believed to have originated in the Indian subcontinent and has been used in Ayurvedic medicine for thousands of years. In India, Ashwagandha is mainly grown in the states of Rajasthan, Gujarat, and Madhya Pradesh. It is also

cultivated in other parts of the country, such as Maharashtra, Uttar Pradesh, and Haryana.

Ashwagandha is also found in other countries in the region, such as Nepal, Pakistan, and Sri Lanka. It is also cultivated in other parts of the world, such as China and Yemen.

The plant is well adapted to grow in arid and semi-arid regions with poor soil conditions and can tolerate high temperatures and minimal irrigation. It prefers well-drained sandy or loamy soils with a pH of 6 to 7.5 and full sun (5).

Phytochemistry

Ashwagandha, also known as *Withania somnifera*, contains a variety of active compounds including alkaloids, steroidal lactones, and withanolides. These compounds are believed to be responsible for its medicinal properties

Some of the major phytochemical compounds found in ashwagandha include:

History of Ashwagandha

Withanolides: These compounds are believed to be responsible for ashwagandha's anti-inflammatory, anti-tumor, and immunomodulatory effects

Alkaloids: Ashwagandha contains a variety of alkaloids, including withanine, somniferine, and anaferine, which are believed to have a calming effect on the nervous system.

Steroidal lactones: These compounds, including sitoindosides and acyl steryl glucosides, are thought to have a positive effect on the immune system and to have anti-inflammatory properties.

Choline: Ashwagandha also contains choline, which is important for brain function and memory. The root of the plant is considered to be the most potent part for medicinal use, however, leaves and berries also contain active compounds (6).

Fig: 2 Phytochemistry , Food Application, Therapeutic Potential of the Plant Withania Somnifera

History of Ashwagandha

The all-out withanolide content went from 0.066 to 0.588% on dry root premise in the increases and upwards of 13 promotions recorded over 0.30%, which are considered economically feasible. The examination of the withanolide profile in these promotions prepared for recognizable proof of prevalent, which recorded higher substance of explicit withanolides of helpful significance viz., withaferin (0.345%), withalonide A(0.125%) and

B (0.068%), with none (0.100%), withanostromalide (0.048%)furthermore, withanoside IV (0.227) and withanoside V (0.042) and nonattendance of explicit withanolides, for example,waithanostromalide, withanone, withanoside V and withanolide B, subsequently showing impressive variety in the assortment for phyto-synthetics. These chemotypes with high satisfaction of explicit mixtures are very significant according to the drug viewpoint (7).

Chemical Constituent and Bioactive Compounds of *Withania Somnifera*

Fig3:- Various phytochemicals present in *Withania somnifera*.

The fresh plant of WS is rich in fatty acids, fatty alcohols, volatile oils, and hydrocarbons, including myristic acid, palmitate, linoleic acid, and straight-chain hydrocarbon hexatriacontane. The roots of ashwagandha include alkaloids (wide variation of 0.13–0.31%), starch, reducing carbohydrates, hentriacontane, glycosides, dulcitol, ethanol acid, and a neutral molecule. In addition, the leaves contain free amino acids including aspartic acid, glycine, tyrosine, alanine, proline, tryptophan, glutamic acid, and cystine. Fruits of Ashwagandha harbour a milk-coagulating enzyme, two esterases, free amino acids, fatty oil, essential oils, and alkaloids. The bioactive chemicals extracted from WS are listed in Figure (8).

ASHWAGANDHA: AN IMPORTANT MEDICINAL PLANT

Withania somnifera (L.) Dunal, usually known as Ashwagandha Indian ginseng or winter cherry, is a famous therapeutic plant in Ayurvedic medicine. The primary dynamic mixtures incorporate a few withanolide-type compounds. Due to its nonhazardous and extraordinary restorative worth,

it is ordinarily utilized everywhere. Roots, and less frequently leaves and organic products, have been utilized as phytomedicines as decoction, mixtures, balm, powder, and syrup. Nowadays, it is developed as a yield to keep up with the popularity of biomass and economic greatness for the necessities of the drug industry. Ashwagandha has been a significant spice in the Ayurvedic and native medication framework for north than 3000 years. It has a place with the family Solanaceae and has a chromosome number of $2n=48$. In India, just two types of *Withania* are found which incorporate *W. somnifera* and *W. coagulans*. This plant has been utilized as a home solution for various illnesses in India and many regions of the planet. It is tracked down in the wild structure in many pieces of the India and the Mediterranean district of North Africa. In India, it is filled in Rajasthan, Madhya Pradesh, Himachal Pradesh, Punjab and Uttar Pradesh. It is assigned as a homegrown tonic and well-being food in the Vedas and is considered as 'Indian ginseng' in the regular Indian medication. It is used as a liver tonic, calming, cell reinforcement, antimicrobial

specialist and solution for asthma. Withaferin-A has been getting a reasonable setup of consideration in light of its anti-infection and antitumor activity. In the Unani arrangement of medication, the underlying foundations of *W. somnifera* typically known as *Asgand* are used for the restorative properties. In Ayurveda, *Ashwagandha* is professed to have compelling Spanish fly-reviving and life-expanding properties. It has by and large invigorating and regenerative capacities and is utilized among others, for the treatment of anxious weariness, sleep deprivation, memory-related conditions, skin issues, sluggishness intensity issues and hacking. It likewise increments learning ability and memory limit. The customary utilization of *Ashwagandha* was to raise energy, energetic power, strength, perseverance, well-being, increment fundamental liquids support the time components of the body, muscle fat, lymph, blood, cell creation and semen. It checks persistent

weariness, lack of hydration, shortcomings, free teeth, bone shortcomings, impotency, thirst, untimely maturing gauntness, muscle pressure, weakness and improvement. It helps fortify the body by reviving the conceptive organs, similarly as a tree is strengthened by taking care of the roots (9).

PHARMACOLOGICAL ACTIVITY OF ASHWAGANDHA

W. somnifera has different pharmacological exercises, calming movement, antibacterial action, antifungal action, antiviral action, antitumour action, immunomodulatory action, hostile to stretch/adaptogenic action, anticonvulsant action, neuropharmacological action, musculotropic action, against oxidant action, hostile to maturing impact, against hyperglycaemic impact, macrophage-enacting impact, hepatoprotective action, morphine resilience and reliance repressing impact (10).

Fig4 - Pharmacological activities of Ashwagandha (*W. somnifera*)

Antibacterial activity of Ashwagandha

Numerous bacterial species have been utilized as a test microorganism for the evaluation of the antimicrobial action of concentrates and refined mixtures of *W. somnifera*. These bacterial strains were *Acinetobacter baylyi*, *Agerobacterium tumefaciens*, *Bacillus cereus*, *Bacillus subtilis*, *Bacillus thuringiensis*, *Chlamydomytila pneumonia*, *Citrobacter freundii*, *Corynebacterium diphtheriae*, *Enterobacter aerogens*, *Enterococcus faecalis*, *Escherichia coli*,

Klebsiella pneumoniae, *Lactobacillus acidophilus*, *Lactobacillus casei*, *Lactobacillus plantarum*, *Lactobacillus rhamnosus*, *Lactobacillus sporogenes*, *Lactobacillus thermophilus*, *Lactobacillus vaginalis*, *Lactobacillus zeae*, *Micrococcus luteus*, *Neisseria gonorrhoea*, *Proteus mirabilis*, *Proteus solanacearum*, *Proteus vulgaris*, *Pseudomonas aeruginosa*, *Pseudomonas fluorescens*, *Raoultella planticola*, *Salmonella typhi*, *Salmonella typhimurium*, *Serratia marcescens*, *Staphylococcus aureus*, *Staphylococcus epidermidis*, *Streptococcus pyogenes*, *Xanthomonas axonopodis* pv. *malvacearum*, *Yersinia*

enterocolitica and not many other Different plant parts viz., calyx, organic product, leaves, blossom, root and stem of Ashwagandha were involved by scientists previously, however, leaves and roots were utilized in the vast majority of the examinations. Various solvents like CH₃)₂CO, benzene, butanol, chloroform, chloroform+hexane, deionised water, diethyl ester, refined water, ethanol, ethyl acetic acid derivation, frosty acidic corrosive, hexane, isopropanol, methanol, oil ether, toluene and water have been utilized for the extraction of compound constituents from different plant portions of Ashwagandha yet methanol was the generally involved dissolvable for the extraction. From the writing overview, we have observed that the circle dissemination strategy was the most favoured technique for the assessment of the antimicrobial viability of Ashwagandha plant removal (11).

Antifungal Activity of Ashwagandha

Before, antifungal action movement has been assessed for different concentrates of various plant portions of Ashwagandha. The point-by-point data on the antifungal action of Ashwagandha is given in the. Many test parasitic species including, *Alternaria brassica*, *Aspergillus flavus*, *Aspergillus fumigatus*, *Aspergillus niger*, *Aspergillus oryzae*, *Candida albicans*, *Candida kefyr*, *Candida tropicalis*, *Cryptococcus neoformation*, *Dreschlera turcica*, *Fusarium oxysporum* f. sp. couple, *Fusarium oxysporum*, *Fusarium verticilloides*, *Penicillium chrysogenum*, *Penicillium citrinum* and *Trichoderma viridae* were utilized for the appraisal of the antifungal

movement of Ashwagandha (12). Different plant parts viz., calyx, bloom, natural products, leaves, root and stem were utilized for the antifungal action appraisal. Generally utilized plant part was the base of Ashwagandha. CH₃)₂CO, benzene, chloroform, ethanol, ethyl acetic acid derivation, chilly acidic. corrosive, hexane, isopropanol, methanol, oil ether, toluene and water (hot and cold) were utilized as dissolvable for the extraction methodology to assess the antifungal movement of different pieces of Ashwagandha. Nonetheless, methanol was the most favoured dissolvable for the extraction of phytochemicals from parts of Ashwagandha. Like antibacterial movement appraisal, the most picked technique for the assessment was the circle dispersion strategy. Notwithstanding, agar well dispersion strategy and toxin food procedure were additionally utilized for the assessment (13).

Probable Role of Withania Somnifera in COVID-19 Pathophysiology

Particularly in suggestive patients, Coronavirus displays pathophysiological achievements, for example, viral passage followed by various clinical signs. A couple of patients progress to resistant reactions with cytokine tempest and hyperinflammation followed by multi-organ disappointment. WS is accounted for to alleviate earlier pathophysiological viewpoints in illness movement and safeguard fundamental organs (Figure). This segment of the survey maps the pharmacological properties upheld by atomic systems of WS to pathophysiological achievements of Coronavirus (14).

Fig 5 Probable Role of Withania Somnifera at various Stages of Covid-19

Immune Homeostasis

An irresistible specialist sets off a neurotic insusceptible reaction organized by the few kinds of safe cells alongside emitted biomolecules. A quick insusceptible reaction to diseases incorporates antigen acknowledgment and phagocytosis. It is trailed by the deferred reaction of irritation. An observational clinical concentrate on disconnected PBMCs of patients with Coronavirus showed raised intrinsic resistance (macrophages and neutrophils) and brought down cell-interceded insusceptibility (B and Immune system microorganisms). The White blood cell reaction is featured to safeguard against viral contaminations including Coronavirus. A watery and hydroalcoholic concentrate of WS and withanolide A fundamentally superior cell-intervened safe reaction. It advanced expansion of B and Lymphocytes alongside Th1 reaction in solid, constantly focused, ovalbumin antigen vaccinated and immunocompromised mice (15).

Cytokine Storm

Viral contaminations, for example, SARS-CoV-2 trigger exorbitant age of favorable to incendiary cytokines known as cytokine storm. Cytokines intervene the cross-talk between resistant cells and tainted cells to clear irresistible specialists.

Hyperinflammation

A part of hyperinflammation features Coronavirus as a persistent sickness. It is described by modifications in cytokine milieu and fiery

pathways. The fiery pathways are intervened through a few elements including cytokines, receptor proteins, inflammasomes, and atomic variables, and so forth. Withanolides have been accounted for to manage the provocative pathways like NF-κB, JAK/Detail, Nrf2, and HIF-1. This favors withanolides in clinical application to oversee ongoing sicknesses related with aggravation.

Vascular Integrity and Alveolar Consolidation

The impact of incendiary arbiters on veins that are conveying them is self-evident. Patients with Coronavirus showed that resistant cells, provocative cytokines, and vasoactive atoms increment holes between endothelial cells that line veins. This prompts vascular spillage that causes penetration of provocative cells. Subsequently, safe cells and cytokines enter recently consumed alveolar space, prompting combination that is apparent through lung imaging. Withaferin A essentially smothered apoptosis of endothelial cells to conciliate disturbance of the blood-cerebrum boundary in a mouse model of horrendous mind injury. An individual vascular penetrability concentrate on uncovered that withaferin A safeguards endothelial boundary in vitro and in vivo.

Inflammation-Induced Organ Failure

The clinical complexities of Coronavirus have been shown to impact different fundamental organs. The foundational incendiary reaction

combined with direct popular relationship with a few organs through the ACE2 receptor enhances the inconveniences. Multi-organ disappointment including liver harm, renal disappointment, and cardiovascular disability adds to death. The fundamental irritation is a conceivable reason for continuous organ disappointment. The incendiary go between delivered by resistant cells course by means of blood and prompt aggravation of a few organs prompting harm. The clinically obvious all encompassing methodology of Ayurveda assigns wellbeing as the main issue of concern. Ayurveda mediations are pointed toward fortifying homeostatic systems and streamlining transformation limits. Dissimilar to the organ-explicit methodology of current biomedicine, Ayurveda centers around foundational renewal to safeguard organs subsequently keeping away from disappointment. WS has arisen as a generally acclaimed organ-defensive medication equipped for potentiating a few organs to battle against contaminations and irritation. This part of the survey features the plausible job of WS in the natural outcomes of irritation prompted organ disappointment in Coronavirus (16).

Brain

The neurological disfigurements are related with Coronavirus pathophysiology. The major clinical perceptions of patients integrate encephalitis, necrotic discharge, and epileptic seizures. A deliberate survey of neurological signs in Coronavirus portrays migraine and anosmia as the most widely recognized side effects.

Neuroinflammation set off by safe cells is a vital instrument to instigate neurological inconveniences. WS leaf fluid concentrate improved provocative cytokine-actuated neuroinflammation by repressing the NF- κ B pathway in the rodent model. A similar concentrate likewise showed a neuroprotective impact by normalizing MAP2 articulation in microglial cells.

Heart

Myocarditis and further heart brokenness are combined with fundamental aggravation. The alcoholic concentrate of WS leaf standardized troponin I discharge in the blood and in this manner saved primary and utilitarian uprightness of contractile myocardium in a rodent model.

Liver

Withanolide-rich division disconnected from WS root methanolic extricate found to reestablish the marker protein levels in drug-actuated hepatic cytotoxicity in rodent models of cytokines. Pre-organization of withaferin A likewise showed the hepatoprotective impact on bromobenzene-prompted injury in a mouse model confirmed by standardized useful proteins. WS root powder standardized carbendazim-prompted histopathological changes in rodent liver.

Lungs

The nasal plot, nasopharyngeal cavity, and lungs are the primary destinations for SARS-CoV-2 contamination. Aspiratory irritation, anosmia, respiratory trouble, and lung endothelial brokenness with endothelitis are the significant side effects related with Coronavirus.

WS has shown defensive impacts against pneumonic fibrosis and lung harm by smothering the statement of development factor b1 in creature studies.

Kidney

The renal framework is likewise observed to be an objective of Coronavirus. Neurotic discoveries detailed direct section of Coronavirus in kidney cells through expanded Pro 2 receptor, while the fiery reaction to disease shows proteinuria and expanded degrees of serum creatinine and urea nitrogen. The fiery instrument is liable for renal brokenness. WS root powder was found to show a nephroprotective impact by balancing out urea nitrogen and creatine level and reestablishing cell reinforcement protein articulation. This is

followed by normalizing histopathological changes in the kidney (17).

Process for extraction of ashwagandha (withania somnifera) roots

BACKGROUND OF THE EXTRACTION:

Withania somnifera, otherwise called Ashwagandha, Indian ginseng, or Winter cherry, is a plant in the Solanaceae or nightshade family. It develops as a short bush (35-75 cm) with a focal come from which branch broadens radially in a star design (stellate) and is covered with a thick matte of woolly hairs (tomentose). The blossoms are little and green, while the ready organic product is orange-red and has milk-coagulating properties. The plant likewise has long brown tuberous roots that are utilized for restorative purposes.

Underlying foundations of Ashwagandha contains steroidal Lactones, Withanosides I, II, III, Glycowithanolides A, D, E, F, G, H, I, J, K, L, M, WS- 1 P and S, alkaloids like withanone, withaferin A, withasomine, somniferine, withanine, cuscohygrine, anhygrine, tropine, pseudotrophine, anaferine, choline, tropanol, pseudotropanol, isopelletriene, withasomnine, starch and so on. The flavor of roots used to be unpleasant and sweet astringent. Attaches used to be 1/3 to 1/2 m long, slender to thick whitish brown from outside, creamish from inside. Withania somnifera is utilized in numerous sicknesses in light of the fact that its constituents meaningfully affect safe framework, sensory system, regenerative framework, circulatory

framework, respiratory framework, stomach related framework, excretory/urinary framework and so forth

Object of the Extraction

Subsequently, the object of the current creation is to give a cycle to extraction of dynamic constituents for example Withanosides IV and Withanosides V from Ashwagandha (Withania somnifera) roots and a drug structure involving said Withanosides, alongside chemically OK excipients, helpful for easing nervousness and stress.

Summary of the Extraction

The current creation unveils an interaction for extraction of Withanosides iV and Withanosides V from Ashwagandha (Withania somnifera) roots, involving the accompanying six significant stages-

1. Sorting and sieving of roots, to remove dust & contaminants
2. Pulverization of roots
3. Cold extraction and filtration
4. Hot extraction and filtration
5. Concentration of extract
6. Drying of extract

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Collection of Materials

The necessary materials for the current examination were gathered from the neighborhood markets of the Jhansi.

Authentication the Sample

Authenticate the sample in Central Ayurveda Research Institute, CCRAS, Jhansi

Preparation of Powder

The dried roots of ashwagandha root were grinded in disc mill. The obtained powder is then allowed to sieve from rotary sieve shaker containing sieves of different mesh no. viz. 30, 60 and 100.

Preparation of ethanolic, acetic and aqueous extracts of ARP (Ashwagandha Root Powder)

The powdered Ashwagandha root samples (50 g/400 mL) were extracted successively with

methanol, acetone and water using soxhlet apparatus at 55- 85 °C 72 h in order to extract the polar and non-polar compounds.

SUMMARY OF THE EXTRACTION

Ashwagandha is a plant commonly used in traditional Ayurvedic medicine and the extraction of its active components is usually done using various methods, including Soxhlet extraction. The Soxhlet apparatus is a type of extractor that uses a continuous hot solvent to extract solids. The process works by immersing the solid sample (Ashwagandha root or leaves) in a solvent that is heated in a flask and circulated through a condenser and back into the flask. The solvent dissolves the soluble components of the plant material, which are then collected in a separate flask.

The Soxhlet extraction method using ethanol as the solvent is a commonly used method for extracting compounds from ashwagandha root.

The process typically involves the following steps

1. Prepare the ashwagandha root powder by grinding it to a fine consistency to increase the surface area for extraction.
2. Place the root powder in a thimble, which is a porous container made of filter paper. The thimble is placed in the Soxhlet apparatus.
3. Fill the flask of the Soxhlet apparatus with ethanol as the solvent. The solvent is heated to a temperature that is suitable for the extraction of the desired compounds from the ashwagandha root.
4. The ethanol solvent is refluxed to extract the compounds from the ashwagandha root. The solvent is distilled and condensed in the condenser and is then collected in the flask.
5. The solvent is then pumped back into the thimble, where it dissolves the compounds from the root powder. The process is repeated several times to achieve the desired level of extraction.
6. After the extraction is complete, the ethanol is evaporated to remove the solvent, and the extract containing the ashwagandha root compounds is obtained.

It's important to note that the exact conditions, such as temperature, pressure, and time, may vary depending on the specific compounds being extracted, and the desired yield.

Fig8. Flow Chart of Ashwagandha Root Extraction Process (18).

ASHWAGANDHA: AN IMPORTANT MEDICINAL PLANT

Without the aid of heat.

a. Desired quantity of base drugs like guggul and jaggery are pounded well in mortar and pestle. Fine powder of drugs are then added in small quantities. When the drug mass attains the required consistency, it is then rolled into pills of desired size and shape. They are later dried in shade and stored in airtight containers.

b. Fine powder of medicinal drugs is taken in khalva yantra/mortar and pestle. Specified liquids like water, cow's milk, swarasa, kwatha, honey etc are added in required quantity. The mixture is triturated until drug mass attains the required consistency. Later the pills of desired size are rolled, dried in shade and stored in airtight containers.

INGREDIENTS

Herbs – Withania somnifera (Dried mature roots) 500mg
 Bulking Agents – Maize Starch 89.75mg, Gum Acacia 18.25mg
 Stabiliser- Polyvinyl pyrrolidone 13mg
 Acidity Regulator - 9.50mg

Ratio of essential components in the preparation of vati

The ratio in relation with fine powder of medicinal drugs is as follows

- Crystallized rock sugar 4 times

- jaggery-2 times
- Guggul and honey-equal proportions Water/ or any other liquid 2 times more than that of Churna used for Vati.

Vati matra (dosage)

karsha (12gms) is the general dosage of the vati or as directed by the physician Vati is administered along with water, honey, milk or any other suitable liquid preparation.

Shelf life

Vati prepared from herbal drugs - 2 years
 Vati of mineral drugs - indefinite time period; no expiry date.

Storage conditions

- Vati or Ayurvedic tablets should be stored so as not to lose their original colour,
- Smell, taste and form.
- They should be preserved in airtight containers.
- When sugar, jaggery or salt is an ingredient, the Vati or Ayurvedic tablets.
- Should be kept away from moisture.

Standardization of vati formulations - Analytical parameters for analysis

- A. Organoleptic parameters:
- 1 Colour: uniform, no mottling
 - 2 Odor: characteristic of the formulation; no disagreeable odor.
 - 3 Taste: sweet
 - 4 Determination of total sugar

5 Determination of Reducing sugar/non-reducing sugar

B. Phytochemical assessment:

- 1 Particle size –approx 10.7 nm
- 2 Identification: Microscopic characters (if vegetable parts are used as ingredients, TLC/HPTLC/HPLC/LC-MS (any one of all)
- 3 Test for heavy/toxic metals - Lead, Cadmium, Mercury, Arsenic
- 4 Microbial contamination - Total bacterial count, Total fungal 5. Test for specific pathogen - E.coli, Salmonella spp., S.aureus, count, Pseudomonas aeruginosa
- 6 Pesticide residue Organochlorine pesticides, Organophosphorus pesticides, Pyrethroids
- 7 Test for Aflatoxins B1, B2, G1, G2

C. Physical evaluation:

- 1 Total ash
- 2 Acid-insoluble ash
- 3 Water-soluble extractive
- 4 Alcohol-soluble extractive
- 5 pH of 5% aqueous solution 6 Volatile oil determination
- 7 Loss on drying at 105 °C

D. Pharmaceutical parameters: In Vitro Parameter

Hardness: Force required to break a tablet in a diametric compression test.

Determined using Monsanto hardness tester or Pfizer hardness tester. Limits: standard compressed tablet 5-8 kg/cm².

Friability: measures the physical strength of the tablet on exposure to mechanical

Shock and attrition. Roche friability tester is used. Limits: % friability 0.5-1.0%.

Thickness: micrometer or vernier callipers is used.

Limits: +5% of the standard value.

Weight variation: Analytical balance I.P limits: If the average weight of the tablet is:

84mg or less $\pm$ 1% 84-250 mg $\pm$ 7.5%

> 250mg -5%

Drug content: if possible

Content uniformity: random sampling 30 tablets. Perform assay for any 10 tablets individually. If the drug content in 9/10 tablets is within the specified limits 85-115% of the label claim then the batch passes. The assay of the 10th tablet should lie between 75-125%.

Disintegration time: not more than 35 minutes, except for tablets formulated with guggul not more than 60 minutes.

Dissolution test: Dissolution is the process in which a solid medicament dissolves in the precise quantity of the given medium. The dissolution property of a dosage form influences the absorption property. Absorption is the prime step for drugs to exhibit their pharmacological action; it has to be studied extensively. Bioavailability studies that describe the in-vivo performance cannot be carried out each and every time. Thus, in-vitro dissolution testing can be considered as a relevant method to predict the in- vivo performance (19-21).

CONCLUSION

Since ancient times, people have used ashwagandha following Ayurvedic treatment. Before ashwagandha extract is widely used for a variety of health conditions and as a supplement, modern science needs proof of its usefulness and safety. The current study found that both male and female participants could safely consume ashwagandha root extract for eight weeks. Future research should, however, look into longer-term studies and different dosage ranges. The usage of ashwagandha root extract in healthy male and female participants was shown to be safe, tolerable, and devoid of any unintended harmful effects. The individuals' measured physical, haematological, and biochemical characteristics fell within normal ranges. To generalize the results, another extensive study is necessary (22, 23).

ETHICAL STATEMENT

It is the responsibility of a pharmacist to act honourably and truthfully. A pharmacist abstains from acts that undermine their commitment to serving their patients' best interests, including discriminatory practices, conduct, and working conditions that impair professional judgment. A pharmacist upholds their level of expertise.

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CONFLICT OF INTEREST

The authors attest that they are free of any known financial or personal conflicts of interest that would taint the findings of this study.

INFORMED CONSENT

Using websites, review articles, and other sources to produce research content.

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